

HURRICANES, HYDROLOGY, AND SEDIMENT: BUILDING AN HMS MODEL OF SEDIMENT YIELD FROM HURRICANES FOR ST. CROIX, U.S.V.I.

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Abstract

St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands, has been impacted by 46 hurricanes or tropical storms in the last 141 years. During that time, the island was hit by hurricane force winds every 7.4 years, on average. These large storm events have had a disproportionate impact on the sediment yield of the island, especially on the drier, eastern end. As part of a larger study of hurricane patterns, sediment cores were collected at two lagoons on the eastern end of the island, South Gate Pond and Great Salt Pond. In order to confirm that layers of coarse sediment contained in these cores were from hurricanes, several HMS models were developed. This development included implementation of the newly developed sediment yield routines in HMS. The annual average sediment yield from the HMS model was compared to the volumes of sediment estimated from the sediment cores and showed a good match. Finally, sediment yields were modeled for three hurricanes in the late 1990s: Lenny (1999), Georges (1998), and Mitch (1998). Based on these three events, sediment delivery to the lagoons can contribute almost half of the annual sediment yield in the span of only a few days.

INTRODUCTION

St. Croix is the largest of the U.S. Virgin Islands at 214.7 km². It is located at 17° 45' N 64° 45' W. Precipitation varies longitudinally across the island, with the West end being relatively wet and the East end receiving less rain. Due to its location, St. Croix has averaged one hurricane every seven to eight years since the late 19th century.

As part of a larger project to study long-term trends in hurricane frequency, sediment cores were collected in two lagoons on the eastern end of St. Croix. South Gate Pond is located on the north side of the island and Great Salt Pond is located on the south side. Both of these ponds are depositional lagoons that act as sediment sinks and may preserve records of sediment delivery due to hurricanes.

METHODS

This study focused on the creation of models for the South Gate Pond and Great Salt Pond watersheds on St. Croix. Neither of these watersheds, however, contains a USGS gage with a long-term record. In order to ensure that the relevant parameters of the hydrology models were realistic, a third model was also created for the Jolly Hill watershed. This watershed contains the only USGS gage on the island with a significant record length. USGS Gage #50345000 (Jolly Hill Gut at Jolly Hill) has continuous 15-minute data available from 1986 through 2006 and was used for calibration. The locations of all three watersheds, as well as the USGS gage, are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Watershed and time series data locations

HEC-HMS 4.0 Alpha was selected for use in modeling the target watersheds. This decision was based on balancing data requirements, ease of model setup, and the implementation of sediment yield routines in the model.

Data gathered for use in the model included the USGS gage flows, topography, soils, and weather information. The soils in the target watersheds are very coarse, primarily gravelly loam. The primary source of meteorological data was a weather station (Christiansted Station; GHCND #VQW00011624) just east of the Great Salt and South Gate Ponds. The weather station records included precipitation data from 1953 to present.

The hydrology model for Jolly Hill on the west side of St. Croix was developed first in order to take advantage of its 20-year flow record. Hydrology models can be very sensitive to certain variables, such as the percentage of impervious surface area and infiltration. For the Jolly Hill watershed model (see Figure 4), calibration was obtained only when a percolation loss of $0.07 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}/1000 \text{ m}^2$ was used, which represents a losing stream condition. Prior to adding the percolation rate the modeled stream overpredicted flow under very small precipitation events.

Figure 2 Eastern St. Croix Topography

Figure 3 Eastern St. Croix Soils

Figure 4 HEC-HMS Model Schematic for Jolly Hill (USGS Gage 50345000)

The year 2001 was selected for calibration of the Jolly Hill model. This year had extreme, moderate, and small events, as well as a complete flow and precipitation record. Figure 5 shows the output of the calibrated hydrology model for this basin.

Figure 5 Calibrated Hydrology Model of Jolly Hill Watershed (USGS Gage 50345000)

The calibrated hydrologic parameters from Jolly Hill were then used in the development of sediment yield models in an Alpha version of HEC-HMS 4.0. The Great Salt Pond and South Gate Pond watersheds were both modeled for hydrology and sediment yield/delivery dynamics. The calibration parameters for the hydrology of the Jolly Hill watershed were used due to its proximity and similarity of the topography, geology, and soil types. The HEC-HMS model layouts for Great Salt Pond and South Gate Pond are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively.

Figure 6 HMS Model Schematic for the Great Salt Pond Watershed

Figure 7 HMS Model Schematic for the South Gate Pond Watershed

The sediment calibration was based on long-term sediment accumulation rates obtained from the sediment cores collected in each lagoon. The physical variables associated with the annual sediment delivery to each lagoon are summarized in Table 1, below.

Table 1 Sediment Calibration Data

	Great Salt Pond	South Gate Pond
Lagoon Area	275,000 m ²	131,000 m ²
Annual Vertical Sediment Accumulation Rate (from Cores)	0.33 cm/yr	0.38 cm/yr
Annual Sediment Accumulation (Volume)	907 m ³ /yr	498 m ³ /yr
Porosity of Sediment (Assumed)	0.53	0.53
Calculated Annual Sediment Yield	1,274 tonnes/yr	699 tonnes/yr

The Great Salt Pond and South Gate Pond HEC-HMS model were divided into 17 annual models from 1986-2005. Calendar years 1989, 1990, and 1994 were excluded from the modeling effort due to insufficient precipitation data. Several other years also had a few days of missing data, although they were not excluded from the modeling. All missing precipitation data were assumed to be 0 mm. The annual sediment yields from the HEC-HMS model are summarized in Table 2.

The average modeled sediment delivery to Great Salt Pond over the 17 selected years was 1,385 tonnes per year. This closely approximates the sediment delivery calculated from the cores of 1,274 tonnes per year. The modeled sediment delivery to South Gate Pond of 542 tonnes per year was comparable to the 699 tonnes per year estimate based on the sediment cores. The sediment yield models for both watersheds were determined to be calibrated based on these results.

Four modern hurricanes were specifically identified as likely signatures in the sediment core record:

1. Hurricane Marilyn – September 14-15, 1995
2. Hurricane Georges – September 19-23, 1998
3. Hurricane Mitch – October 22-23, 1998
4. Hurricane Lenny – November 17, 1999

Upon investigation of the available data for each of these storms, only Hurricane Lenny, Georges, and Mitch were modeled. During Hurricane Marilyn the precipitation gage appears to have malfunctioned and the record does not contain any precipitation. This also leads to an underestimation of the sediment yield associated with the year 1995 in Table 2.

Table 2 Sediment Delivery to Great Salt Pond based on HEC-HMS Sediment Model

Year	Christiansted Precipitation, mm	Great Salt Pond Sediment Yield, tonnes	South Gate Pond Sediment Yield, tonnes
1986	919.7	1,361	530
1987	1,280.8	1,643	638
1988	1,151.3	1,032	411
1989		<i>Insufficient Precip Data</i>	<i>Insufficient Precip Data</i>
1990		<i>Insufficient Precip Data</i>	<i>Insufficient Precip Data</i>
1991	625.8	618	237
1992	957.5	1,443	563
1993	937.6	1,042	407
1994		<i>Insufficient Precip Data</i>	<i>Insufficient Precip Data</i>
1995	860.3	1,462	568
1996	1,353.2	2,782	1108
1997	809.6	1,089	422
1998	1,080.7	1,363	534
1999	1,029.7	1,568	615
2000	773.8	937	367
2001	1,068.5	1,905	747
2002	550.3	489	191
2003	1,428.2	2,283	895
2004	989.5	1,375	531
2005	897.3	1,150	447
Average	983.2	1,385	542

RESULTS

The HEC-HMS models were run separately for each of the three selected hurricanes: Lenny, Georges, and Mitch. The sediment yields resulting from these events, as well as the annual sediment yield for the corresponding year of the calibration runs, are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3 Sediment Modeling Results for Great Salt Lagoon for Selected Hurricanes

Hurricane	Year	Annual Sediment Yield, tons	Hurricane Precipitation, mm	Hurricane Sediment Yield, tons	Percent of Total Annual Sediment Yield
Georges	1998	1,363	100.1	209	15.3%
Mitch	1998	1,363	158.8	499	36.6%
Lenny	1999	1,568	186.9	667	43.0%

Table 4 Sediment Modeling Results for South Gate for Selected Hurricanes

Hurricane	Year	Annual Sediment Yield, tons	Hurricane Precipitation, mm	Hurricane Sediment Yield, tons	Percent of Total Annual Sediment Yield
Georges	1998	534	100.1	82.2	15.4%
Mitch	1998	534	158.8	195.3	36.6%
Lenny	1999	615	186.9	264	43.0%

Since Hurricanes Georges and Mitch occurred approximately one month apart, it is likely difficult to isolate these as two separate events in the sediment record of the cores. Instead, these combined storms may be viewed as yielding 51.9% of the total sediment in calendar year 1998 for both ponds. Figures 8 and 9 show the continuous sediment yield record from the HEC-HMS model for calendar years 1998 and 1999, respectively for the Great Salt Pond. Figures 10 and 11 show the continuous sediment yield record for the South Gate Pond for years 1998 and 1999, respectively.

Figure 8 Great Salt Pond- Calibrated HMS Sediment Yield (1998)

Figure 9 Great Salt Pond- Calibrated HMS Sediment Yield (1999)

Figure 10 South Gate Pond- Calibrated HMS Sediment Yield (1998)

Figure 11 South Gate Pond - Calibrated HMS Sediment Yield (1999)

It should be noted that years with high sediment loads did not necessarily have hurricanes passing directly over the island. In 1996, for instance, Hurricane Hortense did not pass directly over the island but the rainfall generated by the storm still produced a significant portion of the sediment for that year. In 2001, however, a storm in May resulted in a large sediment load. Roughly a third of the modeled years with above average sediment were not the result of hurricanes.

In the sediment yield/sediment routing model, an assumed gradation was provided. The gradation included silts, sands, and gravels. Figure 12 shows the output of the cumulative sediment deposition in the Great Salt Pond by grain class.

Figure 12 Cumulative Sediment Yield in Great Salt Pond Watershed by Grain Size for the 1999 Hurricane Season

Figure 13 shows the output of the cumulative sediment deposition in the South Gate Pond by grain class. Based on the model, there is approximately an equivalent amount of sediment load for the sand, silt, and gravel grain sizes, although there is slightly more sand (approximately 40% sand, 31% silt, and 29% gravel). This is a finer gradation than the Great Salt Pond, even though the same assumed gradation was supplied to the model for the channel bed and parent material in the watershed. This observation (finer sediment in the South Gate Pond) is consistent with observations of the sediment cores at the two lagoons.

Figures 12 and 13 both show the dramatic increase in sediment due to the impact of a hurricane on St. Croix. These sharp changes in sedimentation should be visible in cores taken from the lagoons.

Figure 13 Cumulative Sediment Yield in South Gate Pond Watershed by Grain Size for the 1999 Hurricane Season

CONCLUSIONS

The modeling for the St. Croix watersheds yielded calibrated results for both flow and annual sediment yields in Great Salt Pond and South Gate Pond. It was found from the three hurricanes modeled that the sediment yields associated with a single named storm can contribute almost 50% of the annual sediment yield in that year. In these cases, sediment signatures associated with individual hurricane events may be extracted from sediment cores. Of the sediment that is delivered to the Lagoons, the majority (approximately half) is classified as sand, although the uncertainty associated with this conclusion is relatively high due to lack of sediment gradation data in the stream and in the watershed. The calibrated hydrology and sediment yield model can now be used to answer specific sediment loading questions from other design storms, output from climate change models, or other historic hurricane events. This modeling study demonstrates that the presence of sizeable, distinct layers in cores extracted from Great Salt Pond and South Gate Pond may be good indicators of hurricanes impacting St. Croix.